

ISic2745

I.Sicily inscription 2745

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

Found in re-use in mediaeval period walls above the theatre building

Coordinates

37.967510, 13.197901

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato, Antiquarium Case d'Alia e parco archeologico Monte Iato

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Texts based upon Isler, SEG and comparison with photographs

Translation

Commentary

M. Sève, BE 1988 no.176 suggests reading the name Antallos in line 1. It is very plausible that IGPalermo 40 = ISic1560 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1560>] , found at Monte Iato in 1969, constitutes part of the same inscription.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644843

EDCS 64901086

PHI 331494

PHI 340005

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 50.1002

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 47.1428

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Isler, H. P. 1997. Monte Iato: la ventisettesima campagna di scavo. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 30: 23-44. At 24 fig.7

Isler, H. P. 1987. Grabungen auf dem Monte Iato 1986. *Antike Kunst*. 30: 25-33. At 26-27 fig.1

Isler, H. P. 1986. Monte Iato: la sedicesima campagna di scavo. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 19: 29-48. At 31 fig. 6

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Photo M. Metcalfe